

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF RESIN SOLUTIONS. PART VII. VISCOSITY STUDIES IN MIXED SOLVENTS WITH SOME RESINS AND CELLULOSE DERIVATIVES.

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Viscosity studies in mixtures of two non-solvents having good solvent power or of one solvent and another latent solvent have been made for the following systems over a wide range of temperature and concentration : (i) ester gum in xylene-alcohol, (ii) glyptal in n-butyl acetate-alcohol, (iii) ethyl cellulose in cyclohexanol-cyclohexane, or alcohol-toluene and (iv) cellulose nitrate ($\frac{1}{4}$ ° R. S.) in alcohol-dioxane.

The viscosity curves are primarily of the same type as previously observed for shellac in suitable mixtures. The characteristic features of the curves have been summarised and generalised for different types of solutes.

In continuation of the investigation on viscosity studies of shellac in mixed solvents (Palit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 663 ; 1942, 19, 207) viscosity studies in a mixture of two non-solvents having good solvent power, or of one solvent and another latent solvent (also called active solvent or coupler) of lyophilic solutes other than shellac, have been made in the present communication to test how far the results obtained therein have general validity and significance. Two other resins, *viz.*, ester gum and glyptal, have been selected as subjects of our study, since the former presents a complete contrast to shellac as being insoluble in alcohols but soluble in aromatic hydrocarbons, and since the latter is of a different type being an artificial resin, with peculiarities in solubility. Amongst the other typical lyophilic solutes, we have chosen to work with cellulose nitrate and ethyl cellulose in suitable mixtures of non-solvents. Attempt has also been made to study the protein, gliadin, the prolamine of wheat (which is soluble in a mixture of alcohol and water) but no satisfactory result has been obtained on account of the difficulties arising out of its *denaturation tendency*. Recently, however, studies in precipitation temperature of a similar protein, zein, in mixed solvents have yielded curves (*cf.* Swallen, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1941, 33, 394) similar to those we have obtained for shellac, but no viscosity data are available.

Soaps, which as lyophilic solutes form a class by themselves, have not been studied so far, due probably to the fact that there is not on record any such enhanced solvency in mixtures of solvents. The author (*Current Sci.*, 1941, 10, 436 ; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 271) has lately hit

upon some good mixed solvents for soaps and similar viscosity studies are contemplated. The present study might be of possible industrial importance, since all these substances are employed in the manufacture of lacquers; varnishes, printing ink, etc., viscosity control of which is a matter of considerable importance.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangement, procedure, method of expressing concentration, purification of solvents, etc., are the same as in the previous parts of this series of papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 253, 266).

Preparation and Purification of Materials.—Commercial ester gum of low acid value has been finely powdered (100 mesh) and treated with about twice its weight of pure alcohol. The whole mass swells and becomes sticky by imbibition of alcohol. The sticky mass is occasionally kneaded and the whole left overnight. Three or four such extractions are made until the resin becomes free from colouring matter and acid (acid value, 1 to 2 against alcoholic potash with phenolphthalein as indicator). The resin is freed from solvent in a vacuum oven at 75° and after powdering to hundred mesh is stored in desiccators.

A commercial glyptal of low molecular weight has been used. The resin is white and hygroscopic and is stored in the powdered state in desiccators.

Ethyl cellulose of low viscosity type manufactured by Hercules Powder Co. of U.S.A. has been used.

Cellulose nitrate of half-second R.S. type, manufactured by the same firm has been used. Before use, the alcohol used for damping the substance, has been driven off by heating to 105° for three hours in an air oven.

Ester Gum in Xylene-Alcohol Mixtures.

Ester gum is the glycerol ester of resin; hence the pure gum is abietic triglyceride (mol. wt., 992). The behaviour of ester gum is in many respects different from the already studied case of shellac. Its solutions are less viscous, a 50% solution having a viscosity of only about one-tenth of a poise. Further, a solution, on cooling, does not form a gel, but either separates a flaky precipitate or separates into two liquid layers. Also, due to some steric effect in the complicated molecule of the resin, it comes slowly into equilibrium with its solvent mixture, particularly at its higher

concentrations. Hence, by careful manipulation of the method of preparing the solution, it is possible to study the viscosity and other properties of such solutions as will normally separate into two liquid layers at the temperature of experiment, if allowed sufficient time. Such points as well as those, which show slight haziness during experiment as a result of separation of the solvated resin, are indicated in the graph as dark circles. These points have been included in the graph, as it has been observed that the magnitude of the viscosity change on keeping is of a smaller order.

(A) Viscosity curves in xylene-alcohol mixture.

(B) Precipitation curve in xylene-alcohol mixture.

Viscosities have been studied for 10, 30 and 50% concentrations of the resin at 15°, 20°, 25° and 30°. The data are presented in Table I and viscosity curves in Figs. 1 and 2. The general nature is similar to that observed for shellac in so far as the curves are steeper at higher concentration and lower temperature. Also the minimum viscosity occurs at lesser proportion of the hydroxylic solvent than what corresponds to the minimum in the precipitation curve (so-called optimum solvent composition), and further, like all other previous cases, the minimum viscosity composition progressively approaches the optimum solvent composition with increase in resin concentration.

TABLE I.

Alcohol : xylene.	Viscosity (centipoise) at				Viscosity (centipoise) at			
	15°.	20°.	25°.	30°.	15°.	20°.	25°.	30°.
Ester gum conc. = 10%.								
0 : 100	1'077	0'9842	0'9072	0'8517	3'051	2'721	2'444	2'203
10 : 90	1'074	0'9891	0'9143	0'8435	2'946	2'626	2'361	2'119
20 : 80	1'152	1'058	0'9701	0'8943	2'998	2'679	2'388	2'144
40 : 60	1'320	1'200	1'095	0'9903	3'422	2'985	2'631	2'348
60 : 40	1'511	1'368	1'244	1'126	4'419	3'746	3'206	2'777
Ester gum conc. = 50%.								
Viscosity (centipoise) at								
	15°.	20°.	25°.	30°.				
0 : 100	18'40	15'07	12'57	10'50				
10 : 90	16'20	13'32	11'14	9'43				
20 : 80	16'51	13'50	11'26	9'406				
40 : 60	20'55	16'32	13'26	10'95				
60 : 40	36'13	25'25	18'89	14'60				

The precipitation temperatures have been graphically shown for 20% ester gum solutions (Fig. 1), since for higher concentrations, though the values are accurately determinable at any instant, they slowly change with time. But they all show unmistakable minima at the same region. Curve for 10% ester gum also shows minimum at this region but could not be completely determined since the two solutions at this minimum region have precipitation temperatures below our experimental range, (*i.e.*, below -62° , as produced by solid carbon dioxide and alcohol).

FIG. 2.

Viscosity curves in xylene-alcohol mixture.

These curves have one significant point of difference from those of shellac. Here, the viscosity minimum shifts, if at all, to a very small extent with change of temperature towards a lower concentration of the hydroxylic solvent but the data are not decisive on the point.

It might be pointed out that the minimum in the precipitation curve (so-called optimum solvent composition) is richer in xylene than in alcohol, which according to the view-point previously developed by us, should be attributed to the greater solvent power of xylene than that of alcohol for the ester gum, since xylene can completely dissolve the ester gum while alcohol only swells it. Hence the fact referred to in the previous paragraph may be as follows: a lowering of temperature shifts the minimum towards a higher proportion of the more powerful solvent. This generalisation, however, requires to be tested by a study of further cases of mixed solvency.

Glyptal in Mixed Solvents.

Glyptal has been found to be completely soluble in a mixture of ethyl alcohol and *n*-butyl acetate within the approximate composition range 15:85 to 65:35. From this solubility figure as well as from the fact that alkyds are generally insoluble in aliphatic alcohols but dissolve in some esters and in many benzenoid hydrocarbons, it appears that butyl acetate is a more powerful solvent for glyptal than ethyl alcohol.

FIG. 3.

Viscosity studies have been made at 15 and 25% concentrations at 20°, 25° and 30°. The curves for 15% practically show no minimum, while at 25% concentration, minima in the curves are definitely observed. These curves show no unusual feature and the effect of temperature is not very marked.

TABLE II.

Alcohol : <i>n</i> -butyl acetate.	Viscosity (centipoise), at					
	20°.	25°.	30°.	20°.	25°.	30°.
	Glyptal conc. = 15%.			Glyptal conc. = 25%.		
20 : 80	Insol.	Insol.	—	sl. pptn.	3'821	3'406
30 : 70	1'813	1'641	1'497	4'235	3'714	3'493
40 : 60	1'859	1'679	1'524	4'205	3'693	3'273
50 : 50	1'976	1'773	1'597	4'293	3'766	2'309
60 : 40	Insol.	Insol.	Insol.	4'505	3'937	3'442

Ethyl Cellulose in Mixed Solvents.

Ethyl cellulose is insoluble in hydrocarbons as well as in alcohols but dissolves in their mixtures (Earnst *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1940, 32, 1539). Of the solvents used here, *cyclohexane* seems to have least solvent power for the substance since it swells it to opaque cotton-like flakes, while others very

FIG. 4.

Viscosity curves for ethyl cellulose.

Fig. 4A—1% Ethyl cellulose in *cyclohexanol-cyclohexane*.

“ 4B—3% “ “ “ “ “

slowly produce translucent gels, alcohol being the most powerful in this respect producing practically transparent soft gel. Viscosity studies have

been made with 1, 3 and 5% concentrations of ethyl cellulose in *cyclohexanol-cyclohexane* mixtures at 15°, 20°, 25° and 30° and only 5% ethyl cellulose in alcohol-toluene. The results are given in the following table and are graphically represented in Figs. 4 and 5.

FIG. 5.

Viscosity curves for ethyl cellulose.

„ 5A—5% Ethyl cellulose in *cyclohexanol-cyclohexane*.

„ 5B—5% „ „ „ alcohol-toluene.

TABLE III.

<i>cyclohexanol:</i> <i>cyclohexane</i> .	Viscosity (centipoise) at							
	15°.	20°.	25°.	30°.	15°.	20°.	25°.	30°.
	Ethyl cellulose conc. = 1%.				Ethyl cellulose conc. = 3%.			
10:90	Pptn.	Pptn.	3'267	2'838	Pptn.	31'18	23'70	18'06
15:85	Pptn.	4'084	3'473	3'011	41'18	29'84	22'41	17'35
20:80	5'408	4'537	3'857	3'307	40'02	29'49	22'57	17'70
30:70	7'042	5'843	4'925	4'176	48'90	36'76	28'13	22'06
50:50	14'13	11'39	9'350	7'484	74'20	55'54	42'34	32'75

TABLE III (contd.).

		Viscosity (centipoise) at							
<i>cyclohexanol</i> : 15°.		20°.	25°.	30°.	<i>Alcohol</i> : 15°.		20°.	25°.	30°.
<i>cyclohexane</i> .		Ethyl cellulose conc. = 5%.				Ethyl cellulose conc. = 5%.			
10 : 90	238'9	175'8	117'4	82'47	10 : 90	27'58	23'31	19'90	17'02
15 : 85	181'2	121'7	86'14	63'45	20 : 80	26'72	22'68	19'26	16'32
20 : 80	219'1	150'8	108'1	80'28	30 : 70	26'25	22'21	18'85	16'03
30 : 70	260'5	177'2	129'9	95'88	40 : 60	27'43	23'08	19'54	16'58
40 : 60	349'1	241'5	172'3	125'80	60 : 40	30'76	25'75	21'66	18'27
60 : 40	199'7	130'6	89'8	64'95					

The general appearance of the curves is as usual, 5% and 3% curves showing definite minima at about 16-18% *cyclohexanol*, whereas curves for 1% concentration of ethyl cellulose do not exhibit any perceptible minima. The effect of concentration of the solute is to displace the minimum towards a higher concentration of the hydroxylic solvent. This is evident by comparing the curves at 3% and 5% contents of ethyl cellulose at the same temperature. Since alcohol is a more powerful solvent for ethyl cellulose than hydrocarbons, *cyclohexanol*, which is a hydroxylic solvent, is presumably so. This shift of minimum therefore only shows that an increase in concentration of the solute displaces it to an increased proportion of the more powerful solvent. Though the optimum solvent composition in this system could not be determined due to experimental difficulties, to be referred to later, it can be reasonably assumed from considerations of solvent power of the individual solvents, that it is certainly somewhere containing greater proportion of *cyclohexanol*. Hence the effect of concentration becomes the same as in the previous cases, *i.e.*, a shifting of the minimum towards the so-called optimum solvent composition.

The effect of decrease in temperature, as may be noted from the curves, is to displace the minimum towards a greater proportion of the more powerful solvent. This trend is also clearly observable from the curves for 5% ethyl cellulose in alcohol-toluene mixture (Fig. 5B), a system which is much less viscous than the previous one.

The study of precipitation or gelation temperature of this system and other systems to be described later, could not be made as the temperatures are often inconveniently low and have lesser degree of reproducibility than that of shellac.

Cellulose Nitrate in Alcohol-Dioxane.

This is virtually the same as studying the classical case of nitrocellulose in alcohol-ether (Gibson and McCall, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1923, 39, 1721) with the advantage that the cyclic ether 1-4 dioxane is much less volatile

(b.p. 101.5°) than ordinary ether. Cellulose nitrate is soluble in this mixture containing from about 50 to 95% dioxane. From this figure on solubility, as well as from the fact that the cellulose nitrate used is of the ester-soluble type, it is easily intelligible that dioxane is a better solvent than alcohol. The above argument concerning solubility and solvent power needs elaboration. Of the two non-solvents, A and B, if A requires less B to dissolve a certain quantity of the lyophilic solute than the proportion of A, which is required by B to produce the same solubility, we shall term A, the more powerful solvent. That this is in agreement with facts is borne out by the various solubility diagrams of resins obtained previously by the author. Now, to make dioxane a solvent for nitrocellulose we have to add 5% alcohol to it, whereas to make alcohol a solvent we have to add about 50% dioxane; hence, dioxane is by far a more powerful solvent of the two.

Viscosity studies have been made for 5, 10 and 15% concentrations of cellulose nitrate at 15°, 20°, 25° and 30° (Fig. 6).

TABLE IV.

Alcohol : dioxane.	Viscosity (centipoise) at			
	15°.	20°.	25°.	30°.
	Nitrocellulose conc.=5%.			
10 : 90	23.37	20.29	17.61	15.33
20 : 80	19.01	16.50	14.45	12.69
30 : 70	16.48	14.35	12.54	11.04
40 : 60	15.52	13.54	11.87	10.39

Alcohol : dioxane.	Viscosity (centipoise) at							
	15°.	20°.	25°.	30°.	15°.	20°.	25°.	30°.
	Nitrocellulose conc.=10%.				Nitrocellulose conc.=15%.			
10 : 90	168.8	139.3	116.1	97.12	1195	931.1	775.7	613.5
20 : 80	141.3	118.8	100.2	84.55	820.8	671.9	549.6	450.7
30 : 70	121.1	102.1	85.90	72.78	595.3	485.6	393.4	322.5
35 : 65	114.2	95.76	80.72	68.13	548.9	443.0	361.6	296.3
37.5 : 62.5	116.0	97.25	81.94	68.84				
40 : 60	136.0	112.6	93.56	77.69	803.5	643.9	515.2	418.6

The effect of increasing concentration is the same as in the previous cases. For example, there is no viscosity minimum observable at 5% concentrations, whereas minima occur at 10 and 15% nitrocellulose. The minima are at one end close to the solubility limit and more slowly drifts with increasing concentration towards the centre, *i.e.*, a higher concentration of dioxane, presumably towards the optimum solvent composition as shown in the previous cases.

The effect of temperature is found to be the same as in the previous cases, a decrease of temperature tending to displace the minimum towards a higher proportion of the more powerful solvent. This effect is more pronounced with the curves for 15% than for 10% concentration.

C O N C L U S I O N S .

Both in the present as well as in the previous papers the following general trends, which we have been able to recognise in such viscosity curves, have been pointed out :

The viscosity curves exhibit minimum above a certain concentration of the lyophilic solute, the sharpness of the minimum increasing with increase of concentration and decrease of temperature.

The shape of the viscosity curves as well as its dependence on concentration and temperature have already been discussed with reference to the gelation capacity of the system in a previous section of this part.

With increasing concentration, the minimum gets shifted towards, and tends to approach the optimum solvent composition.

The latter may, of course, for all practical purposes, be taken as that solvent composition at which the gelation tendency is the least, but it may be formally defined as that composition of the solvent mixture which will produce gelation with the highest concentration of the solute at any given temperature. It is borne out by observations that the relative proportion of the two solvents in the optimum composition represents their relative solvent power.

With decreasing temperature, the minimum moves slowly towards a higher proportion of the more powerful solvent or more probably towards the optimum solvent composition.

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